

Synthesis and analytical application of a new chelating resin containing 8-aminoquinoline group

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Amberlite IRC-50 has been functionalized by 8-aminoquinoline group and the resulting resin has been characterized by elemental analyses, infrared spectra and metal ion capacities. The present resin is very useful for preconcentration, separation and sequential determination of trace amounts of copper and zinc by atomic absorption spectrometry. Parameters such as the amount of the resin, effect of pH, equilibration rate, sorption and desorption of metal ions, effect of diverse ions have been studied. The procedure has been applied to the determination of copper and zinc in several biological samples including three certified materials after their dissolution by microwave-assisted treatment. The proposed method has a good accuracy.

Copper and zinc are both micro-nutrient as well as toxic elements for living beings, depending upon the concentration level. Moreover, copper/zinc ratio in biological samples is of great importance because it has significance not only in diagnosis of cancer¹ and cardiac activity² but also in determining optimal nutrition³. So the interference free determination of these metals is very essential.

The application of chelating resin produced by the chemical modification of solid matrix offers a good possibility in trace metal preconcentration. Anchoring the active site to a solid support in a polymer matrix provides an immobilized active surface capable of selective and quantitative separation of cations from aqueous solutions. The developed procedure has been used to selectively remove and preconcentrate specific cations from the synthetic mixture of metal ions, environmental samples, recovery and purification of precious metals, separation of components from nuclear wastes⁴. Separation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} has been achieved by many workers using the chelating resins containing various chelating groups like imidazole⁵, 4-(2-thiazolylazo) resorcinol⁶, pyrogallol⁷, pyrocatechol⁸, 6-mercaptopurine⁹ etc.

Solid surfaces having heterocyclic donor sites have specific activity towards transition metal ion¹⁰. 8-Aminoquinoline (AQ) contains heterocyclic nitrogen donors and incorporation of this ligand into polymeric matrix may lead to a solid surface which may be effective for the separation of copper and zinc from each other.

In this work, we shall demonstrate that 8-aminoquinoline resin gives a high rate of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} sorption making it possible to separate them from biological samples. The use

of microwave oven for the dissolution of different type of environmental samples appear to be very attractive because it is very fast¹¹. Procedures based on microwave-assisted digestion have been reported by several workers for copper and zinc determination in biological materials¹² but in these cases digestion conditions differ for different metals. Thus there is a strong need for a reliable analytical procedure which can be applied to the determination of both these metals, particularly at very low level. Nevertheless, atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) is the general method of choice for copper and zinc detection due to high sensitivity of these elements.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of the resin :

The resin was synthesized by the procedure shown in Scheme 1 and the results of the elemental analysis of AQ

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the resin.

resin are given in Table 1. The nitrogen content of the final resin was found to be 4.72% corresponding to 3.4 mmol g⁻¹ of the dry resin. Given that every 8-aminoquinoline has 2 nitrogen atoms, we took 1.68 mmol of the functional groups per gram of the resin as the theoretical capacity. If

Table 1. Physical and chemical characteristics of the AQ resin

Bead size	30–60 mesh
Thermal stability	240°
Equilibration time (min)	
for Cu ^{II}	20
for Zn ^{II}	22
IR data	3307 cm ⁻¹ for N–H for, 1698 cm ⁻¹ for C=O and 1384 cm ⁻¹ for C=N stretchings. Other bands at 1176 cm ⁻¹ , 823 cm ⁻¹ , 345 cm ⁻¹ for 8-aminoquinoline moiety

the resin : metal is 1 : 1 then the capacity should be 1.68 mmol g⁻¹ but actually it is found only 0.81 mmol g⁻¹ for Cu^{II}. Steric factor probably lowers the result.

In addition to elemental analysis, resin characterization was carried out by IR spectroscopy in order to determine the chemical nature of the functional group within the matrix. The IR spectra of the polymers are complicated and only few peaks could be assigned with reasonable certainty. The infrared spectrum of the final resin was compared with the starting copolymer and it was found that the band due to C–Cl stretching at 698 cm⁻¹ was disappeared. On the contrary, some new bands appeared at 3307 cm⁻¹ for N–H, 1698 cm⁻¹ for C=O and 1384 cm⁻¹ for C=N indicating the incorporation of 8-aminoquinoline moiety. Other bands at 1176 cm⁻¹, 823 cm⁻¹, 345 cm⁻¹ etc. also confirmed the proposed structure (Table 1).

The time required for 50% uptake of the maximum capacity for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} was found to be 20 and 22 min respectively. This shows that the resin is suitable for column operation under a low flow rate condition.

Sorption and desorption of metal ions :

The sorption behaviour of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} on the resin was studied by batch method. The maximum capacity for Cu^{II} at pH 5.5–6.0 is 0.81 mmol g⁻¹ and for Zn^{II} at pH 4.5–5.0 it is 0.62 mmol g⁻¹. The effect of different eluents on the desorption of metal ion is given in Table 2. It is observed from Table 2 that the use of different eluting agents viz. 1 M SSA and 1 M HCl for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} respectively permits their sequential separation.

Effect of diverse ions :

Separation of 2 µg ml⁻¹ each of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} from several binary mixtures of various foreign ions in a sample volume of 50 ml at pH 6.0 were carried out. The presence of macro amounts of diverse metal ions like alkali and alkaline earth metal ions of the first transition series did not interfere (Table 3). Desorption of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} was done with almost 100% recovery using suitable eluent as already described. Hence

Table 2. Desorption of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} by different eluents

Eluents	% recovery	
	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
0.01 M HCl	21.6	16.9
0.1 M HCl	58.7	43.6
1.0 M HCl	99.3	101.2
2.0 M HCl	101.6	103.1
0.01 M HNO ₃	18.7	14.6
0.1 M HNO ₃	46.9	49.8
1 M HNO ₃	101.6	99.7
0.25 M SSA	63.1	nd
1 M SSA	102.3	nd
4 M SSA	103.1	nd

nd = not detectable.

Table 3. Separation of 2 µg ml⁻¹ of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} from various foreign metal ions in a sample volume of 50 ml at pH 5.0 for both

Foreign ion*	% recovery	
	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
Fe ^{III}	96.3	98.2
Cd ^{II}	103.2	93.6
Hg ^{II}	98.1	94.4
Mn ^{II}	101.3	102.1
Cr ^{III}	97.4	95.3
Na ^I	99.9	100.9
Ni ^{II}	98.7	100.3
Co ^{II}	97.2	98.9
Ca ^{II}	101.1	99.1
Ag ^I	100.8	98.6
PO ₄ ³⁻	97.7	96.1
SO ₄ ²⁻	102.1	102.8
NO ₃ ⁻	96.1	97.8

* In each case added foreign metal ion was 2000 µg.

attempts were made to separate Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} from binary synthetic mixtures, various certified and real biological samples viz. mussel tissue, chlorella, unpolished rice flour.

Applications :

Separation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in the binary synthetic mixtures :

100 µg each of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were mixed in 100 ml of double distilled water and passed through the column loaded with 1 g of AQ resin after maintaining the pH at desired level. Sorbed Cu^{II} was eluted completely with about 10 bed volume 1 M neutral SSA and sorbed Zn^{II} was eluted completely with 25 ml 1 M HCl. The result shows that 98.9% Cu^{II} and 99.0% Zn^{II} can be recovered from the binary mixtures of these two ions (Table 4).

Table 4. Separation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in binary synthetic mixtures

No. of observation	Amounts taken μg	Amounts found μg	% Error
1.	Cu ^{II} : 10	Cu ^{II} : 10.3	3.0
	Zn ^{II} : 100	Zn ^{II} : 102.1	2.1
2.	Cu ^{II} : 100	Cu ^{II} : 98.7	1.3
	Zn ^{II} : 10	Zn ^{II} : 9.6	4.0
3.	Cu ^{II} : 50	Cu ^{II} : 51.9	3.8
	Zn ^{II} : 100	Zn ^{II} : 98.5	1.5
4.	Cu ^{II} : 100	Cu ^{II} : 96.7	3.3
	Zn ^{II} : 50	Zn ^{II} : 52.2	54.4
5.	Cu ^{II} : 50	Cu ^{II} : 53.1	6.2
	Zn ^{II} : 50	Zn ^{II} : 46.7	6.6

Separation and estimation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in of biological samples :

The biological samples were digested using microwave oven by the procedure described earlier. Amount of each biological samples taken and the results of analysis are indicated in Table 5.

Table 5. Separation and estimation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in biological samples

Sample (g)	Certified value ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	Obtained value ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	% Error
Mussel tissue (0.1051)	Cu : 7.96	Cu : 7.93	0.25
	Zn : 156.25	Zn : 159.1	0.24
Chlorella (0.2639)	Cu : 3.50	Cu : 3.31	7.71
	Zn : 20.50	Zn : 22.80	2.10
Rice flour unpolished (0.2974)	Cu : 3.50	Cu : 3.40	2.85
	Zn : 25.20	Zn : 24.80	1.58

Experimental

Equipment : Atomic absorption spectrometric measurements were made with a GBC Avanta AAS with the following conditions viz. for copper : lamp current 4 mA, wave length 324.7 nm; for zinc : lamp current 5 mA, wave length 213.7 nm. pH measurements were made on a Systronics digital pH meter (model 362). A domestic SAMSUNG 2933 microwave oven with a 2450 MHz frequency magnetron and 900 W maximum power was employed to carry out the digestion of different samples assayed inside home-made polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) reactors, with 115 ml internal volume, 1 cm cell wall thickness and hermetic screw caps.

Reagents : Stock solutions of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were obtained from E. Merck (Germany). Working standard metal solutions were prepared by appropriate dilutions. The following reference materials were analyzed : MA-M-2/TM

mussel tissue (sample no. 325 of International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria, reference materials), NIES 3 *chlorella* and NIES 10 *rice flour* (both NIES certified reference materials from National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan Environment Agency). All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Microwave-assisted digestion of samples :

For complete dissolution of different types of biological materials, sample mass quantities from 105.0 to 297.4 mg were taken in a hermetically sealed PTFE reactor. A 4 ml 14 M HNO₃ at 450 W power level for 3 min and 3 M H₂O₂ at 450 W for 4 min was used stepwise for complete digestion of biological sample. Finally, digestion at 450 W for 3 min ensures the total decomposition of these matrices. After digestion, each of the solutions were diluted with water to a final volume of 25 ml.

Synthesis of the resin :

Air dried Amberlite IRC-50 containing a carboxylic group was used as starting material. The polystyrene beads (5 g, 30–60 mesh) were swollen in distilled chloroform and separated by filtration. The carboxylic group resin is now chlorinated by the use of PCl₅ in distilled chloroform by stirring for 10 h at room temperature. The chlorinated product was then allowed to react with 8-aminoquinoline using triethylamine as base. The resulting chelating AQ resin then dried by a vacuum drier and preserved at room temperature for further use.

Metal ion capacity as a function of pH :

Batch sorption procedures were applied in order to determine the resin capacity for metal in the pH range 1.0–6.0. 100 mg of the AQ resin were taken in a 100 ml beaker and excess metal ion solution (1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was added. pH of the above solution was adjusted either by the addition of dil. HCl or sodium acetate buffer throughout the equilibrating period (24 h) until it remained constant at the desired level. Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} concentrations were determined by using atomic absorption spectrometer using air-acetylene flame.

Studies of various eluting agents for desorption :

The resin containing maximum absorbed metal ions were shaken with 30 ml of various eluting agents e.g. HCl of different strengths and neutral 5-sulphosalicylic acid (SSA) for 24 h. After filtration the amounts of each of the metal ions in the filtrate were determined by AAS.

Column operation and effect of diverse ions :

A glass column of 130 mm length and 10 mm i.d. was used for the present investigation. Air dried AQ resin (1 g) was immersed in double distilled water and allowed to flow

through the solution so that large particles occupy bottom position to avoid choking problem. The resin column was thoroughly washed with the solution of appropriate pH.

The sorption and recovery characteristics for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in the presence of various metal ions were thoroughly examined. A 100 ml portion of the mixture of the test metal ion and foreign metal ions was allowed to flow through the resin column at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. The metal ions not sorbed by the resin were completely washed out using hydrochloric acid solution of pH 5.0 and 5.5 respectively for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}. Sorbed Cu^{II} was eluted completely with about 25 ml 1 M neutral SSA and sorbed Zn^{II} was completely eluted with 25 ml 1 M HCl.

Conclusion :

The results show that resin containing 8-aminoquinoline group is very selective for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} due to the presence of heterocyclic nitrogen of the pyridine moiety and may be followed by chelation via N atom of amide residue. The resin thus has an immense potentiality for the effective preconcentration of trace copper and zinc from biological matrices. Microwave-assisted digestion followed by AAS allows reliable determination of these two metals in biological samples in which copper and zinc may be present at very low levels. Thus the present method for the determination of copper and zinc in biological samples is an attractive one.

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